

An Intersectional Exploration of War Literature and Environment

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Abstract

This research article digs into the complex nexus between war literature and the environment, revealing the various ways in which armed conflict and the natural world cross in literary narratives. This article tries to illuminate the growing representation of the environment against the backdrop of conflict by evaluating a varied variety of texts spanning different historical periods, genres, and cultural settings. The study begins with the phenomenon of how war is worshipped in literature, looking at how landscapes, ecosystems, and the larger environment have traditionally been represented as both victims and witnesses of battle in war literature. It demonstrates how to use vivid and emotive language to depict the environmental toll of conflict, putting light on ecosystem loss, community relocation, and the long-term ecological scars left by combat. The study focuses on select works from English and Tamil Literature that focus on war and the ideas of the environment. It would be helpful to know the harms of war and the need to preserve the environment for the younger generation.

Keywords: Environment, War, Literature, Ecology, Historical Context.

Introduction

War literature emphasizes the importance of the environment in influencing the experiences and psyches of both troops and civilians. It investigates how the natural environment influences human behaviour, mental health, and survival methods during combat. War is violence. It can be better defined as:

War is a species in the genus of violence; more specifically it is collective, direct, manifest, personal, intentional, organized, institutionalized, instrumental, sanctioned, and sometimes ritualized and regulated, violence. These distinguishing features and dimensional delineations are not limitative. It should be perfectly clear, however, that war, or the state of belligerence, is a very special category of violence (Van der Dennen, 1977).

The literary studies reveal repeating themes of resilience, adaptability, and the fundamental link between individuals and their environment in times of conflict through a comparative investigation of narratives from various worldwide areas and historical eras. Furthermore, the study looks at the agency of the environment in war literature, looking into how natural elements are personified, anthropomorphized, or symbolically loaded with significance. It investigates how authors use the environment as a powerful metaphor to represent the larger sociopolitical and moral implications of battle. War can be,

Closely related to a political definition of war is the judicial conception. Q. Wright (1942; 1965) describes war as “a legal condition which equally permits two or more hostile groups to carry on a conflict by armed force”. The Marqués de Olivert is quoted as declaring that “war is a litigation or suit (litigio) between nations that defend their rights, in which force is the judge and victory is the judicial award”. This analogical and figurative characterization of war is perhaps more literary than factual (Bernard, 1944).

Furthermore, the study digs into the ethical implications of environmental degradation in the setting of armed conflict, emphasizing the critical importance of ecological consciousness in both literary representation and real-world conflict resolution. The comparative study provides a thorough examination of the complicated connection between war literature and the environment. It gives unique insights into how war narratives connect with and reflect on the natural world by synthesizing ideas from literary studies, environmental humanities, and cultural analysis. **“A healthy ecology is the basis for a healthy economy” (Claudine Schneider)** This study contributes significantly to the developing subject of Eco-criticism by providing a nuanced understanding of the devastating impact of armed conflict on the ecosystem, as well as the reciprocal influence of the environment on the human experience of war. To stop war and protect the environment is vital today. In the Tamil didactic work *Tirukural*, there is a kural that points out that all evils are from vile matters; especially war, but all goodness comes from friendship; which means good nature. **All evils come from enmity All goodness flow from amity (Kural 860)**

War in Tamil and English literature

War literature, a genre inextricably linked to the human experience, is a potent medium for portraying the tremendous impact of armed war on individuals, societies, and nations. It offers a forum for delving into the many dimensions of war, from its cruelty and confusion to the tenacity and heroism that frequently emerge amid the tragedies of warfare. There are different aspects of war in Tamil and English literature, two separate traditions with contrasting perspectives on combat, conflict, and the human condition. Songs from the first to third century CE are included in ancient Tamil literature, known as Sangam literature. One of the Sangam works is *Aintinai*. It says about the eminence of nature.

Aintinai, or the five-fold categorisation of the environment into Kurinci, Mullai, Marutam, Neidal and Palai, combined with the corresponding flora and fauna, should be seen as the earliest attempt by the Sangam poets towards the formulation of an environmental aesthetics... (Murali 157)

Many of these poems reflect warriors' bravery and sacrifices in combat. They frequently honour troops' valour and highlight the emotional cost of war on people and communities. “Kalingathu Parani” is written in the form of a narrative poem that extols the Chola monarchs and their military might. It beautifully recounts the Chola army's splendour, triumphant wars, and the conquering of Kalinga. The poem contains detailed descriptions of battles, scenery, and Chola troops' valour (Redyar, 1957). In “Kalingathu Parani”, there is a scene of goriness of war. So it must be avoided.

Kalingappei is said to convey the nature of war to Kali. The actions of the four armies, the intense warfare, the news that the two armies were matched against each other when Karunakara launched his spear, the destruction of many of the

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four armies on both sides, the King of Kalinga running away and hiding from the fierceness of the battle, the news that Karunakarathondaiman sent spies with his forces to find him, and the Kalinga warriors hiding on a mountain top. The news has been beautifully told that when he came to know about the stand it was evening and did not fight, he waited till dawn and destroyed Kalinga, Kalinga warriors fled in all directions and went to Kulothungan with his charmed wealth and bowed down there. (War)

During the Chola dynasty (9th to 13th century CE), epic poetry such as “Silappatikaram” and “Manimekalai” dealt with war and its effects. These works investigate the human drama and moral quandaries that develop in the setting of war. The immense collection of material created mostly in the English-speaking globe that is war literature (English Literature) illustrates the global effect of war throughout numerous historical periods and conflicts. It covers literature from World Wars I and II, as well as the Vietnam War and more current wars such as the Iraq and Afghanistan Wars. Authors such as Wilfred Owen, Erich Maria Remarque, and Tim O’Brien have made significant contributions to this tradition. Poetry, fiction, memoirs, and non-fiction narratives are all examples of war in English literature. These works investigate the physical and mental toll of war on troops and civilians, tackling issues such as the futility of war, the loss of innocence, the dehumanizing impacts of warfare, and the difficulties of post-war reintegration. These accounts frequently serve as moving criticisms of the political and socioeconomic reasons that push nations to war, as well as the grave moral problems that arise during battle. Thus, war gives unique insights into the human experience of conflict, albeit from distinct cultural and historical viewpoints in both Tamil and English literature. While Tamil literature relies on an old heritage, English literature represents the modern era’s worldwide reach of armed conflict. Both traditions share the purpose of giving testimony to the intricacies of war and shedding light on the long-term effects it has on persons and society.

Common comparative themes

- Human Tragedy: Both Tamil and English literature frequently emphasize the human tragedy and suffering that comes with conflict. They show the physical and emotional toll that people, families, and communities take. However, they also stress more importance to the environment and to avoid war.
- Heroism and Sacrifice: Both traditions honour the bravery and sacrifice of warriors. They delve into the concepts of honour, responsibility, and bravery in the face of hardship.
- Critique of war: Some works act as criticisms of war in both Tamil and English literature. They call into question the justification for war and emphasize its harmness.
- Cultural and Historic Context: The cultural and historical backdrop of the societies in which the literary works are produced frequently influences the depiction of conflict. This influences the views and subjects investigated. Both cultures are related to the glorification of nature.

The Impacts

Warfare and military conflicts may have immediate and terrible environmental consequences. This includes environmental harm, pollution, deforestation, and habitat destruction. During active warfare, for example, woods may be blasted, rivers contaminated, and wildlife destroyed. The environmental consequences of war can last long after the battle

has finished. Unexploded ordnance, chemical contaminants, and other dangers can remain, endangering both humans and the environment (Austin,2000). War is frequently waged over access to resources such as oil, minerals, and fertile land. Because these resources are harvested without sufficient attention for sustainable practice, they might cause environmental devastation. War can cause large-scale population relocation, putting strain on local habitats. Refugees may place a strain on resources such as water, food, and shelter, potentially resulting in overuse and deterioration. Jeremy points out the problems of war as:

The cultural and ideological aspects of war also repay examination. They focus on the importance of arousing, channelling and legitimating violent urges, and of persuading people to fight, kill and run the risk of being killed, without which there is, and can be, no war. The willingness to kill is crucial to the causes of war and is a conflation of long-term anthropological and psychological characteristics with more specific societal and cultural situations. (Jeremy 42)

During battles, ecosystems are frequently disturbed or destroyed, resulting in biodiversity loss. “Species may be driven to extinction or suffer catastrophic population decreases. Evidence shows that climate change might worsen existing tensions by changing environmental circumstances (such as droughts or resource scarcity)”. There is thus an indirect relationship between ecology, the environment, and the possibility of conflict. Peace and stability, on the other hand, are critical for environmental rehabilitation. Post-conflict rebuilding initiatives must incorporate environmental restoration and sustainable development measures. The connection between conflict, ecology, and the environment is complex. War has major and generally devastating environmental consequences; conversely, environmental factors can play a role in conflict. It is critical to handle these relationships.

Environmental facet of War novels

“The Blue, the Grey, and the Green” (2015) is one of just a few works on the Civil War that take an environmental history perspective. This book investigates how environmental disease, climate, flora and fauna, and other factors influenced the war, as well as how the conflict influenced Americans’ views, knowledge, and use of nature. The writer, Brian Allen Drake employs a variety of “methodologies that will serve as a useful blueprint for future environmental histories of the war”. “Natural Enemy, Natural Ally: Towards an Environmental History of War” (2004), by historian and environmental expert Richard Tucker is a major study in the topic of environmental history. The book dives into the complex link between armed conflict and the environment, providing a thorough assessment of how conflicts and military actions have impacted, and been shaped by, the natural world. According to the book, conflict works as a “catalyst for environmental change” (Tucker,2004), hastening processes like deforestation, land degradation, and urbanization. This viewpoint contradicts the commonly held belief that environmental damage is primarily the result of peaceful activity. Tucker thoroughly examines the environmental implications of combat, which include deforestation, soil erosion, and pollution, as well as habitat devastation and wildlife upheaval. The book emphasizes how these effects have ‘far-reaching ecological, social, and economic consequences’. Jacob Darwin Hamblin wrote the book “Arming Mother Nature: The Birth of Catastrophic Environmentalism.” It was published in 2013 and delves into the history of ecology, geopolitics, and military strategy. The novel is set during the Cold War, a time of increased geopolitical tensions between the United States

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and the Soviet Union. There was a rising interest at the time in the possible military uses of environmental technology. The phrase “catastrophic environmentalism” is used by Hamblin to characterize the concept that large-scale environmental disruptions may be purposefully created to suit military and geopolitical purposes. Weather alteration, climate engineering, and ecological warfare are all examples of this. Some literary works examine the deep relationship between war literature and the environment and have shown a significant and multifaceted connection. **“Earth provides enough to satisfy every man's need, but not every man's greed.” (Mohandas K. Gandhi)** A thorough examination of literature from various historical eras and cultural contexts reveals that armed conflict not only reshapes human society but also has significant impact on the natural world. **“Preservation of our environment is not a liberal or conservative challenge; it's common sense.” (President Ronald Reagan)** The literature reviewed graphically depicts the environmental conflict, portraying battle-scarred landscapes, damaged ecosystems, and uprooted communities. It serves as a sobering reminder of the far-reaching impacts of armed warfare, emphasizing the critical necessity for environmental awareness during times of war.

The poets of Sangam age minutely observed how the climate of a region and its natural resources lend something to their own energy and to the character of its inhabitants and how their manners and modes of life undergo an imperceptible change owing to their influence. In fact, those were days when man was more dependent upon Nature and therefore his habits and tastes were moulded by his environment and he himself was more or less a product of Nature's handiwork. The poets fill the poems of “Akam” by getting tint and colour from Nature and have made their poems produce everlasting interest not only to man's life but also to Nature, itself. Wordsworth's observation, “The world is too much with us” absolutely reflects the perceptions of “Akam” poets. (Uma Ramamoorthy 95)

Uma points out the importance of ecology and the environment through the Sangam poems in comparison to words worth the concept of nature. It will prove that war is deterioration and nature is life. Furthermore, this approach indicates the environment's critical role in influencing individuals' experiences and psyches during conflict. The natural environment serves as both a refuge and a threat, affecting survival choices and altering mental well-being. Even in the most extreme conditions, this nuanced picture emphasizes the inherent link between individuals and their environment.

Conclusion

The study adds to the larger conversation on environmental humanities by shining light on the often-overlooked ecological elements of war. It emphasizes the need to document the environmental costs of war as well as advocate for sustainable practices, peace-building initiatives, and a better understanding of the intricate web that connects human cultures and the natural world. Recognizing this inherent link leads to a more complete and compassionate understanding of the consequences of armed conflict on our world, as well as the responsibility to protect both human and environmental well-being.

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